

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D6.1: Implementation of CMEMS-MSCS Interfaces

WP6: Implementation of new interfaces and methodologies in
coastal systems

30-06-2025/v1.0

Funded by
the European Union

About this document

Title	D6.1: Implementation of CMEMS-MSCS Interfaces
Work Package	WP6, Implementation of new interfaces and methodologies in coastal systems
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Reviewers	K. Johnson (Hereon), J. Staneva (Hereon)
Due Date	30.06.2025, M18
Submission Date	29.06.2025
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
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FOCCUS: Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-CL4-2023-SPACE-01: Strategic autonomy in developing, deploying and using global space based infrastructures, services, applications and data 2023. Start date: 01 January 2024. End date: 31 December 2026.

Funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement **No. 101133911**). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health

and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

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Glossary and Abbreviations

BGC	Biogeochemical
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	National Research Council (Italy)
CRMSE	Centered Root Mean Square Error
CRPS	Continuous Rank Probability Score
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DCSM	Dutch Continental Shelf Model
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
FOCCUS	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users
HABs	Harmful Algal Blooms
HEREON	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MET.NO	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
MHD	Marine Hydrographic Directorate (Romania)
ML	Machine Learning
MSCS	Member State Coastal System (s)
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
PU	Public
PUM	Product User Manual
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
S	Salinity
SCHISM	Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydroscience Integrated System Model
SHOM	Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine (France)
SD	Standard Deviation
SHYFEM	System of Hydrodynamic Finite Element Modules
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SWAN	Simulating WAves Nearshore
T	Temperature
WP	Work Package
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WQ	Water quality
WW3	WaveWatch III®
XBEACH	Cross-shore Beach Dynamics Model

1. Executive summary

The **FOCCUS project** (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to improve and advance the coastal dimension of CMEMS and demonstrate a convincing leverage and coupling of CMEMS and Member State Coastal System (MSCS) for advancing knowledge about the coastal environment and associated applications.

Work Package 6 (WP6) focuses on strengthening the **connections between MSCS and CMEMS** through the application of **innovative nesting methods** and new data fusion approaches using stochastic simulations, ensemble approaches and AI technologies.

This report provides an overview of all MSCS, assesses the current status of biogeochemical (BGC) mapping and describes the newly implemented nesting methods per MSCS. Thereby, this report summarises the work on:

- **Subtask 6.1.1** Parameter mapping: Mapping of MSCS with respect to nesting requirements with focus on BGC models, where integration is the most challenging.
- **Subtask 6.1.2** Implementation of new nesting capabilities: Better utilisation of CMEMS products in MSCS.

Out of the status assessment of biogeochemical mapping, it is recommended to:

- Extend the distribution of ammonium to both hindcast and multi-year products for more regions.
- Harmonise efforts between different products, with the ultimate aim to have identical variables in all released products.

Fourteen new interfacing techniques have been used to successfully improve interfacing of CMEMS into the MSCS. Out of the improvements, four have implemented nudging techniques, three have improved the model numerics or physics, two use new wave modelling techniques and two have changed their technical implementation. The four other improvements use bias corrections, update model surface forcings, use ensemble techniques and initialise nesting in CMEMS to improve the interfacing. In the next steps of the FOCCUS project, as part of **Work Package 7**, these nesting techniques will be tested and the improvements will be validated to quantify the added value of the improved nesting techniques.

The document is structured to provide an overview of the wide array of newly implemented nesting techniques and the MSCS in which they are applied. **Section 2** provides an overview of all MSCS used throughout the FOCCUS project, both in a summary table and through individual fact sheets. **Section 3** provides the outcomes of subtask 6.1.1, where the frequent users of biogeochemical models describe how CMEMS BGC products are currently implemented and share recommendations on how to improve this. **Section 4**, which is based off [MS6.1](#) (see [Annex](#)), describes the wide variety of newly implemented ways in which the connection between MSCS and CMEMS is strengthened through new nesting techniques.

2. Overview of Member State Coastal Systems (MSCS)

This chapter serves as an overview of all Member State Coastal Systems that are being worked on. Until system number 12, the MSCS worked on in this deliverable is described (in blue/white). Afterwards, MSCS are described that are used for other tasks in Work Package 6, not related to nesting improvements (in yellow). Factsheets of all MSCS are presented as reference material. Further details on these MSCS are also available in this [Inventory of Coastal Systems](#) (see [Annex](#)).

Table 2. Overview table of MSCS used in FOCCUS.

#	MSCS name	Lead	Coverage (area of interest)	CMEMS interface based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	Short description of nesting work and expected improvements based off MS6.1 (see Annex)
1.	3D DCSM-FM	DELTA RES	North Sea/Dutch Continental Shelf	Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Hindcast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving consistency in physics between CMEMS NEMO and 3D DCSM-FM on thermobaricity: taking pressure into account in the Equation of State. This will result in improved stability in the oceanic areas of 3D DCSM-FM. [BETTER] - Replace current SPM forcing with weekly SPM CMEMS satellite, gap-filled with 4DVarNet. This will result in a more accurate weekly SPM field that can be applied to 3D DCSM-FM. [FORC]
2.	Norkyst	MET Norway/N ERSC	From the Kattegat along the Norwegian coast to the Barents Sea	Arctic Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast Baltic Sea Physics Analysis and Forecast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving lateral boundary conditions using analysis increments from 4D-Var to assess inconsistencies between Norkyst and the CMEMS models. [BETTER]
3.	CROCO-MANG A	SHOM	French Atlantic coast	Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast Global Ocean Physics Ensemble Reanalysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of oceanic ensemble simulations (GLO4ens) at the open boundaries, to quantify the sensitivity of our regional system to uncertainties from remote regions. [ENS]

				<i>(not distributed yet)</i>	
4.	Tolosa-SW	SHOM	French Atlantic coast	Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish-Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering of the non-barotropic dynamics of IBI / GLO products. It is expected that taking into account physical processes not currently represented in Tolosa-SW will improve water level forecasts. [BETTER] - In parallel, development of ML-assisted calibration, trained via IBI datasets in particular, to assess the impact of non-barotropic processes on ssh bias. [BIAIS]
5.	GCOAST-GB	HEREON	German Bight	Atlantic - European NWS Physics Analysis and Forecast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Nesting approach of the GCOAST-GB into the (IBI_MFC) was improved by in addition to apply 3d time series at the boundary line of elements, also to apply relaxation to daily temperature and salinity fields to gain an improved thermohaline field. [NUDG]
6.	GCOAST-BS	HEREON / MHD	Northwestern Black Sea	Black Sea Physics Analysis and Forecast Black Sea Waves Analysis and Forecast Black Sea, Bio-Geo-Chemical , L3, daily Satellite Observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved operability using parametric 2D wave spectra computed from CMEMS wave analysis and forecasting products. This approach avoids running a basin-scale wave model (e.g., WW3) to generate spectral forcing for SCHISM. [WAVE]
7.	Lazio Coastal Areas	CMCC	Tyrrhenian Sea	CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Analysis and Forecasts -PHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Addressing the effect of different frequency for lateral boundary forcings to improving the simulation accuracy of the MSCS. [TECHN]
8.	DKSS	DMI	Baltic-North Sea	CMEMS NWS MFC Multi-Year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Addressing effects of non-local static sea level impacts at the lateral boundary condition - Reducing initial error in subsurface T/S fields by nudging CMEMS products. [NUDG]

				Product-PHY; CMEMS BAL MFC Multi-year Product-PHY; CMEMS NWS MFC Analysis and Forecast - WAV; BAL MFC Analysis and Forecast - WAV; WAV TAC NRT and MYP products; SST TAC NRT and MYP products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aggregating CMEMS forecasts, national forecasts and satellite observations to provide multi-forecasts based ensemble forecast (SST and Waves).
9.	OPTOS v3	RBINS	North Sea/ Belgian Coastal Zone	CMEMS Atlantic-European North West Shelf-Ocean Physics Reanalysis (NWSHELF_MULTI YEAR_PHY_004_0 09) OSTIA SST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lateral Boundary condition of salinity/temperature to the first 3D domain in the nested chain of domains, NoS (North Sea). [NEST] [NUDG] - Accurate downscaled salinity and temperature fields at the lateral boundaries of the NoS domain, ensuring smooth and realistic transitions from external forcing data into the nested model domain.
10.	SHYFEM-CNR	CNR-ISMA R	Adriatic Sea	CMEMS MED-MFC physical multiyear product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nudging of T/S MED-REA over the whole Adriatic basin using spatially variable relaxation coefficient. [NUDG]
11.	MOHID-LisOcean	+Atlantic	Tagus and Sado estuarine areas, Portugal	Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Downscaling wave model using CMEMS IBI Ocean Wave Analysis and Forecast. [WAVE] - Improve the forecast capability of coastal circulation and wave propagation through one-way coupling between a circulation model (MOHID) and a wave model (SWAN). [TECHN]

				<p>Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast</p> <p>Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast</p> <p>Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish-Ocean Wave Analysis and Forecast</p>	
12.	Adri-FS	CMCC	Adriatic Sea	CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Analysis and Forecasts -WAV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Downscaling wave model using wave spectra rebuild from CMEMS wave analysis and forecasting products. [WAVE] - Improve model forecast skills through a new variational scheme for coastal data assimilation. - Improved wave uncertainty estimation through ensemble technique with perturbation of the air-sea exchange parameters. [ENS]
13.	WMOP	SOCIB	Western Mediterranean Sea	<p>CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Analysis and Forecast products (Clementi et al., 2017) - 1/24, daily</p> <p>CMEMS Mediterranean Sea physical reanalysis (Simoncelli et al., 2014)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve model forecast skills through multi-platform data assimilation, including new data source: high-resolution altimetry data (Sentinel-6A-HR-20Hz (Vergara et al., 2025) from WP2. - Improvement of the forecasting capability of mesoscale dynamics in coastal areas - Expected improvements on surface currents, height, temperature and salinity fields

				in-situ assimilated (Argo & mooring T-S profiles); land-based remote sensing (HF radar Ibiza Channel); satellite (SLA along-track, L4 SST);	
14.	NEMO-ORUST50 + OpenDrift	SMHI	Orust-Tjörn fjord system at the Swedish west coast		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presently no plans for improvements in nesting - long-term goal for interfacing with CMEMS: provide HAB forecasts for the local mussel farm industry based on Copernicus Marine Model products, by training ML algorithms on the NEMO-ORUST50/OpenDrift output.

2.1. MSCS “3D DCSM-FM” (Dutch Continental Shelf)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Dutch Continental Shelf Model Flexible Mesh
Description	Three-dimensional model for the computation of water levels, currents and temperatures. Coupled with the D-Water Quality module, which simulates physical, chemical, and biological processes in surface waters. D-Water Quality covers a range of substances and processes in water systems, such as oxygen, nutrients, algae growth and suspended matter.
Source	Numerical Models
Spatial extent	Lat [43° to 64°] · Lon [-15° to 13°] ¹
Spatial resolution	varies from ~5-7 km to ~800-900m
Temporal extent	2015-2017 (spin up 2012-2014)
Temporal resolution	Hourly · Daily
Depth levels	Vertical resolution: 20 σ -layers in the top 100m and underneath (max 30) z-layers
Variables	Sea surface height (SHH) Temperature (T) Salinity (S) Eastward sea water velocity (UV) Northward sea water velocity (UV) Vertical velocity (W) Nutrients: Ammonium - NH ₄ , Nitrate - NO ₃ , Phosphorus - PO ₄ , Silicate - Si Plankton biomass (DIAT_X, DINO_X, FLAG_X, Phae_X - (X \in [E, N, P]))

¹ In all tables, latitude is given in degrees north and longitude in degrees east.

	Dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) Dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) Suspended Matter (SPM) Total Inorganic Matter (TIM) Chlorophyll-a (CHL) Dissolved oxygen (O2) Potential Hydrogen (pH).
Feature type	unstructured grid/mesh
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	None
Update frequency	Not operational, used for planning and scenario studies
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	Deltares
External Link	https://iplo.nl/publish/pages/132741/factsheet-noordzee-dfl-owfm3d_dwaq-v2022_v1.pdf

2.2. MSCS "Norkyst" (Norway)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Norkyst-DA
Description	Assimilative coastal ocean forecasting system based on ROMS with 4D-Var covering the coastal areas of mainland Norway. Other variants of this modeling system exist.
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Coastal area · Lat [55.0° to 75.7°] · Lon [-4.4° to 36.5°]
Spatial resolution	2.4 km
Temporal extent	From 01/12/2017
Temporal resolution	Hourly · Daily
Depth levels	42
Variables	Sea water potential temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S)

	Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) Eastward sea water velocity (UV) Northward sea water velocity (UV) vertical velocity Salinity vertical diffusion coefficient Barotropic sea water x velocity Barotropic sea water x velocity
Feature type	Grid
Projection	Polar stereographic
Data assimilation	HF radar radials · In-Situ Salinity and Temperature · SST
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	MET Norway
External Link	https://ocean.met.no/models#norkyst https://thredds.met.no/thredds/projects/foccus.html https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS

2.3. MSCS “CROCO” (France)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	CROCO-MANGA
Description	CROCO-based coastal ocean forecasting system in development to replace the current HYCOM-based operational system in the Bay of Biscay and English channel region.
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Coastal area · Lat [39.9° to 52.6°] · Lon [-15.0° to 4.8°]
Spatial resolution	1.9 km
Temporal extent	TBD – <i>not operational yet</i>
Temporal resolution	Hourly · Daily
Depth levels	32 σ -levels
Variables	Sea water potential temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S) Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) Northward sea water velocity (UV) Eastward sea water velocity (UV)
Feature type	Grid
Projection	Mercator

Data assimilation	Not yet
Update frequency	TBD – not operational yet
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	Shom, France
External Link	Will be made available at https://data.shom.fr (HYCOM-based OFS currently available)

2.4. MSCS “Tolosa-SW” (France)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Tolosa-SW
Description	Shallow water version of the Tolosa toolbox used for surge forecasting; in use in the French national forecasting system
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Coastal area · Lat [43° to 61°] · Lon [-9° to 10°]
Spatial resolution	10 km offshore · up to 50m nearshore
Temporal extent	From 06/09/2024
Temporal resolution	10 min (1D) · Hourly (2D)
Depth levels	Depth-averaged outputs
Variables	Total water height (h) Sea surface height (SSH) Zonal Velocity (U) Meridional Velocity (V)
Feature type	Triangular unstructured grid

Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	Daily
Format	CSV (1D) · Binary, VTK (2D)
Provider	Shom, France
External Link	https://data.shom.fr/

2.5. MSCS “GCOAST-GB” (German Bight)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	GCOAST-GB
Description	Based on SCHISM, covers German Coastal Waters
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Lat [53.0° to 55.6°] · Lon [5.1° to 10.4°]
Spatial resolution	Cross-scale 1.5 km - 100 m horizontal resolution
Temporal extent	From 01/12/2017
Temporal resolution	Hourly, Daily
Depth levels	21 vertical layers using sigma coordinates
Variables	Temperature (T) Salinity (S) Sea surface height (SSH) Velocity (UV) Vertical velocity (W) Wave significant height (SWH) Wave mean period (MWT) Wave Peak Period (VTPK) Wave mean direction (VMDR) Suspended matter (SPM)

Feature type	Triangular unstructured grid (native, distributed as gridded 0.005 degree)
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon GmbH
External Link	HCDC TDS Catalog

2.6. MSCS “GCOAST-BS” (Northwestern Black Sea)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	GCOAST-BS
Description	Based on SCHISM, this setup covers the Northwestern Black Sea shelf. The SCHISM is coupled with wave (WWM) and sediment (SED3D) models, providing physical, sea state, and sediment-related variables.
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Lat [41.2° to 46.7°] · Lon [27.4° to 31.6°]
Spatial resolution	Cross-scale 3 km - 100 m horizontal resolution
Temporal extent	TBD – not operational yet
Temporal resolution	Hourly, Daily
Depth levels	LSC ² up to 18 vertical coordinates
Variables	Temperature (T) Salinity (S) Sea surface height (SSH) Velocity (UV)

	Vertical velocity (W) Wave significant height (SWH) Wave mean period (MWT) Wave Peak Period (VTPK) Wave mean direction (VMODR) Suspended matter (SPM)
Feature type	grid/mesh
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	TBD – <i>not operational yet</i>
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon GmbH / MHD
External Link	Will be made available at The Helmholtz Coastal Data Center (HCDC - https://thredds.hcdc.hereon.de/thredds/catalog/catalog.html)

2.7. MSCS "Lazio coastal areas" (Italy)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Lazio coastal areas forecasting system
Description	Coastal ocean forecasting system based on SHYFEM-MPI and WW3 covering the coastal areas of Western Mediterranean.
Source	Numerical models: SHYFEM-MPI WW3
Spatial extent	~ Lat [41.7° to 42.5°] · Lon [11.2° to 12.2°]
Spatial resolution	from 2 km off-shore to 30 m along the coast
Temporal extent	From 2022

Temporal resolution	Hourly
Depth levels	56
Variables	Sea water potential temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S) Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) Velocity (UV) Wave Significant Height (SWH) Wave MeanPeriod (MWT) Wave Mean Direction (VMDR)
Feature type	Triangular unstructured grid
Projection	Mercator
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	CMCC
External Link	https://civitavecchia.cmcc.it/

2.8. MSCS "DKSS" (Denmark)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Danish Storm Surge Model in the Baltic-North Sea
Description	DKSS provides operational 3D ocean forecasts, with 7 two-way nested domains in the Baltic-North Sea region, with focus on Danish waters. It uses a three-dimensional, two-way nested, coupled ocean-ice model HBM.
Source	Numerical models: HBM (HIROMB-BOOS Model)
Spatial extent	~ Lat [48.5°N to 65.9°N] · Lon [4.1°W to 30.3°E]
Spatial resolution	from 5 km off-shore to 185 m in fjørd areas
Temporal extent	From 2010
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Depth levels	10-52 z-levels, varying with sub-domains
Variables	Sea water potential temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S)

	Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) Eastward sea water velocity (U) Northward sea water velocity (V) Sea ice concentration (SIC) Sea ice thickness (SIT)
Feature type	Regular latitude-longitude grid
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	4 times per day
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	DMI
External Link	https://ocean.dmi.dk/models/hbm.uk.php

2.9. MSCS "OPTOS v3" (Belgian Coastal Zone)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Operational Forecasting System for Belgian Coastal zone, OPTOS-BeC
Description	A multi nested domain coastal forecasting System based on the model COHERENS.
Source	Numerical Model COHERENS
Spatial extent	Longitude :- 0.3000° E to 4.6333° E Latitude :- 49.7333° N to 52.7000° N
Spatial resolution	~145 m / ~116 m
Temporal extent	From 2019

Temporal resolution	Hourly
Depth levels	10 Sigma Layers (BeC)
Variables	Temperature (T), Salinity (S), Barotropic velocity (UV), Vertical velocity (W), Sea surface height (SSH), Horizontal and Vertical diffusivity
Feature type	Structured Lat-Long grid
Projection	WGS-84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	daily
Format	netcdf
Provider	RBINS
External Link	None

2.10. MSCS "SHYFEM-CNR" (Italy)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Shyfem-CNR Adriatic Modelling System
Description	Shyfem-CNR Adriatic Modelling System is the application of the unstructured SHYFEM model to a computational domain that represents the whole Adriatic Sea, the lagoon of Marano-Grado, the lagoon of Venice and the Po River Delta (including the Scardovari and Goro lagoons). The spatial resolution of the triangular elements varies from 4 km in the

	open sea to a few hundred meters along the coast and tens of meters in the inner lagoon and river channels.
Source	Numerical models: SHYFEMcm-ISMAR
Spatial extent	Lat [40.0° to 45.8°] · Lon [12.1° to 19.9°]
Spatial resolution	Cross-scale 4 km - 10m horizontal resolution
Temporal extent	2016
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Depth levels	77
Variables	Sea water temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S) Sea surface height (SSH) Eastward sea water velocity (U) Northward sea water velocity (V)
Feature type	Triangular unstructured grid
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	Not operational, used for hindcast simulations
Format	NetCDF
Provider	CNR-ISMAR
External Link	None

2.11. MSCS "MOHID-LisOcean" (Tagus and Sado Estuaries, Portugal)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	LisOcean Operational Model
Description	The 3D LisOcean Operational Model system is based on the MOHID and SWAN numerical models applied for the coastal area covering the Tagus and Sado estuarine areas, in Portugal. The operational models provide a 3-days forecast of hydrodynamic and water properties and 5-days forecast of wave conditions.

Source	Numerical models: MOHIDWater and SWAN
Spatial extent	Lat: 38.16° to 38.96°N Lon: 8.66° to 9.65°W
Spatial resolution	280 m
Temporal extent	Hydrodynamics: 15/10/2023 – up to date Waves: 01/01/2025 – up to date
Temporal resolution	Hourly 2D fields, 3-Hourly 3D fields; Daily
Depth levels	7 Sigma Layers (0-8.68 m) + 37 Cartesian Layers (8.68-3037.72 m)
Variables	Salinity (S), Temperature (T) Velocity (UV), vertical velocity (W), Sea Surface Height (SSH), Wave Significant Height (SWH), Wave Mean Period (MWT), Wave Mean Direction (VMDR).
Feature type	Structured regular grid
Projection	WGS84
Data assimilation	None
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF, HDF5
Provider	+Atlantic
External Link	https://thredds.atlanticsense.com/

2.12. MSCS "AdriFS" (Italy)

Description	Coastal ocean forecasting system based on SHYFEM-MPI and WW3 covering the coastal areas of Western Mediterranean.
Source	Numerical models: SHYFEM-MPI WW3
Spatial extent	~ Lat [39° to 45.8°] · Lon [12.1° to 19.8°]
Spatial resolution	from 2.5 km off-shore to 100 m along the Italian coast
Temporal extent	From 2022
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Depth levels	102
Variables	Sea water potential temperature (T) Sea water salinity (S) Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) Velocity (UV) Wave Significant Height (SWH) Wave MeanPeriod (MWT) Wave Mean Direction (VMDR)
Feature type	Triangular unstructured grid
Projection	Mercator
Data assimilation	No
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	CMCC
External Link	https://adri.cmcc.it/

2.13. MSCS "WMOP" (Spain)

Description	Assimilative coastal ocean forecasting system based on ROMS with EnOI covering the coastal areas of Western Mediterranean.
Source	Numerical models: ROMS - The Regional Ocean Modeling System
Spatial extent	Coastal area · Lat [34.9° to 44.7°] · Lon [-5.7° to 9.1°]
Spatial resolution	2 km
Temporal extent	From 2014
Temporal resolution	3 Hourly · Daily
Depth levels	32
Variables	Temperature (T) Salinity (S) Sea surface height (SSH) Velocity (UV) Vertical velocity (W)
Feature type	Grid
Projection	Mercator
Data assimilation	Argo profiles, Satellite altimetry, Satellite SST, HF Radar data, Buoy data. Satellite altimetry and SST data from CMEMS are utilized for both data assimilation and model validation.
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	SOCIB modelling@socib.es
External Link	https://www.socib.es/en/what-we-do/ocean-forecasting/wmo p

2.14. MSCS "NEMO-ORUST50 + OpenDrift" (*Orust-Tjörn fjord system*)

INFORMATION	
Full Name	Nemo3.6-ORUST50
Description	high resolution Nemo3.6 setup covering the complex Orust-Tjörn fjord system at the Swedish west coast.
Source	Numerical Model Nemo3.6 (and OpenDrift)
Spatial extent	Coastal area ~ Lat [57.816° to 58.483°] · Lon [11.111° to 11.945°]
Spatial resolution	50 m
Temporal extent	2016 and 2022
Temporal resolution	hourly
Depth levels	Nemo3.6: 31 (OpenDrift: surface)
Variables	(potential) Temperature (T) Salinity (S) Velocity (UV) Vertical velocity (W) Wind at 10 m (WIND)
Feature type	Nemo3.6: regular grid (OpenDrift: trajectories)
Projection	none
Data assimilation	no data assimilation applied
Update frequency	not operational
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	SMHI

External Link	none
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3. Biogeochemical (BGC) mapping of MSCS for nesting in CMEMS

This chapter covers the outcomes of Task 6.1.1. Parameter mapping: Mapping of MSCS with respect to nesting requirements, with focus on BGC models. Consortium partners which use CMEMS products in their BGC models describe the BGC model and the current nesting methods. Per partner, these findings are summarised in a table, displaying the MSCS state variables, conversion from CMEMS and assumptions that are used. At the end of the chapter, common findings are summarised and recommendations are made to improve the BGC mapping of MSCS within CMEMS products.

3.1 Use of CMEMS in BGC model - 3D DCSM-FM

The DCSM-FM consists of two computational parts, the D-Flow FM and D-Water Quality. The former is used to compute the hydrodynamics, combining tides, waves and currents. D-Water Quality is fully integrated with and online coupled to these hydrodynamics and solves additional equations for transport, physical, biogeochemical and biological processes to model the (environmental) quality of the water system. The active substances, undergoing transport by advection and diffusion processes, are oxygen (OXY), ammonium (NH₄), nitrate (NO₃), phosphate (PO₄), silica (Si), biogenic silica (Opal), particulate organic carbon (POC), particulate organic nitrogen (PON), particulate organic phosphorus (POP), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), dissolved organic nitrogen (DON), dissolved organic phosphorus (DOP) and various species of phytoplankton. It is these substances that need to be initialised at the boundaries when setting up a biogeochemical model.

Concentrations of the active water quality constituents at the open boundaries are derived from the CMEMS GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_BIO_001_0029 product, which provides biogeochemical data at a 0.25-degree horizontal resolution and for 75 vertical levels. This product is preferred due to its temporal extent, which is also suited for hindcasting scenario studies.

Two types of assumptions occur when converting the CMEMS data into MSCS state variables, see Table 3.1:

- **Unit conversions:**
OXY, NO₃, PO₄ and Si can be directly derived from CMEMS, where only the unit from CMEMS (mmol/m³) is converted to the unit of the MSCS state variable (mg/l)
- **Conversions based on literature:**
Opal, POC, PON, POP, DOC, DON, and DOP cannot be directly derived from CMEMS, as these variables are unavailable. However, with some assumptions of different molar ratios, biomass and per cent of offshore dissolved organic material (Redfield, 1934; Brzezinski, 1985; Agatova et al., 2008; Letscher et al., 2015), these MSCS state variables can be calculated from CMEMS.

For the other MSCS state variables (NH₄ and various phytoplankton species), no conversion is possible from CMEMS, and the values are assumed to be 0 at the boundaries.

Table 3.1: The conversion from CMEMS to MSCS state variable for the DCSM-FM, and the assumptions that they rely on. Green: Unit conversion. Yellow: Literature-based conversion. Red: No conversion possible, assumed to be 0 upon initialization.

MSCS State Variable	Conversion from CMEMS	If assumed, assumption relies on
OXY	CMEMS_OXY * 32/1000	
NH ₄	NONE	Not available from CMEMS. 0
NO ₃	CMEMS_NO3* 14/1000	
PO ₄	CMEMS_PO4 * 31/1000	
Si	CMEMS_Si * 28/1000	
Opal	CMEMS_PHYC * (28/1000) * 0.5 * 0.13a	a= C:Si ratio Brzezinski (1985), 50% of phytoplank carbon biomass is diatoms
POC	CMEMS_PHYC * 2 * 12/1000b	b= carbon detritus ratio of 2
PON	CMEMS_PHYC* 2*(16/106)*(14/1000)c	c= using molar Redfield C:N:P ratio (106:16:1) (Redfield,1934)
POP	CMEMS_PHYC* 2*(1/106)*(30.97/1000)c	c= using molar Redfield C:N:P ratio (106:16:1) (Redfield,1934)
DOC	CMEMS_PHYC * (91.8/8.2)*2*(12/1000)	d=Assuming 91.8% of offshore organic matter is dissolved (estimate for waters of the shelf currents from (Agatova et al., 2008))
DON	CMEMS_PHYC * (19/225)*(91.8/8.2)*2*(14/1000)e	e=Using a molar C:N:P ratio of 225:19:1 (global average export stoichiometry of semi-labile dissolved organic matter below 100m estimated by (Letscher et al., 2015))
DOP	CMEMS_PHYC * (1/225)*(91.8/8.2)*2*(30.97/1000)e	e=Using a molar C:N:P ratio of 225:19:1 (global average export stoichiometry of semi-labile dissolved organic matter below 100m estimated by (Letscher et al., 2015))
Phytoplankton (DIAT_X,DINO_X, FLAG_X, Phae_X, (x= E,N,P))	NONE	Not available from CMEMS. 0

3.2 Use of CMEMS in BGC model - GCOAST

For the coupled physical-biogeochemical configuration of the GCOAST model, CMEMS biogeochemical data sets are used for model forcing, model calibration and model validation. Specifically nutrient variability has been retrieved from the Copernicus Marine Service, of NWSHELF_MULTIYEAR_PHY_004_009, such as daily nitrate, phosphate and silicate. The data was sampled from the Copernicus product in the area of a 10 km sponge layer along the GCOAST model domain open boundary to provide a forcing on daily time scale in this area. For calibration of plankton growth via late attenuation, the optical product OCEANCOLOUR_NWS_BGC_HR_L3_NRT_009_203 has been accessed. Besides the spatial sampling, the reanalysis data provided by CMEMS require linear conversions to match the units used by the GCOAST model. These conversions are further described in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: The conversion from CMEMS to MSCS state variable for the HEREON BGC model. Green: Unit conversion. Red: No conversion possible, no boundary condition imposed (BGC) or set to zero (SPM).

MSCS State Variable	Conversion from CMEMS	If assumed, assumption relies on
NO3	CMEMS_NO3 * 79.5*1e3	coupled with NEMO-ERSEM (which is used by CMEMS)
PO4	CMEMS_PO4 * 106*1e3	coupled with NEMO-ERSEM (which is used by CMEMS)
NH4	NONE	
SiO4	CMEMS_SIL * 79.5*1e3	only available from climate projections but not reanalysis
OXY	CMEMS_OXY	
Phytoplankton	CMEMS_PHYC *1/12	
Zooplankton	NONE	
SPM	NONE	

3.3 Use of CMEMS in BGC model - LisOcean WQ

The LisOcean Water Quality (WQ) model includes a biogeochemical (BGC) module designed to simulate key nutrient and biological dynamics in coastal and Tagus/Sado estuarine systems. The BGC model is configured to receive input from the IBI- Ocean Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast (IBI_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_005_004) product. Relevant variables for the studied domain such as oxygen (OXY), nitrate (NO3), phosphate (PO4), silica (Si), chlorophyll (CH1a), and phytoplankton are converted from the CMEMS units to the model's internal units according to Table 3.3. IBI_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_005_004 product provides biogeochemical data at a 0.028° horizontal resolution and for 50 vertical levels. This product is preferred due to its spatial resolution and extent.

Table 3.3: The conversion from CMEMS to MSCS state variable for the +ATLANTIC BGC model. Green: Unit conversion. Red: No conversion possible, assumed to be 0.

MSCS State Variable	Conversion from CMEMS	If assumed, assumption relies on
OXY	CMEMS_OXY * 0.031987	Converted to mg/l
NH4	NONE	Not available from CMEMS.
NO3	CMEMS_NO3* 0.0140067	Converted to N-mg/l
PO4	CMEMS_PO4 * 0.030974	Converted to P-mg/l
Si	CMEMS_Si * 0.028086	Converted to Si-mg/l
CH1a	CMEMS_CH1a	
Phytoplankton	CMEMS_PHYC * 0.01201	

3.4 Conclusion and recommendations

The three described approaches to nesting BGC models in CMEMS have two common issues:

1. Ammonium (NH_4) is not available in some multi-year and hindcast products for the GLOBAL or North Western Shelf products, whilst it is an important variable in the BGC models. Especially when modelling biogeochemical processes in the coastal zone, the contribution of NH_4 is an important process, which cannot be initialised properly due to a lack of data.
2. Through discussions, another common issue that arose was the consistency in variables between biogeochemical products of different regions. An example of this is silicate (Si), which is not available in the Atlantic-European North West Shelf Ocean Biogeochemistry Reanalysis product. However, it is available in the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Hindcast product. As a result, to set up a boundary for silicate in the North Western Shelf area, users are forced to use a product of coarse resolution for some variables, and finer resolution for others. It takes multiple products to set up the biogeochemical model.

Therefore, there are two recommendations.

1. We recommend extending the distribution of NH_4 to both hindcast and multi-year products for more regions.
2. We also recommend that CMEMS product owners implement harmonisation efforts between products, aiming to have identical variables in all products.

4. Implementation of CMEMS-MCSC interface improvements

The following chapter describes the implemented interface improvements between the Member State Coastal Systems and CMEMS products, subject to [Task 6.1.2](#). Per MSCS, the improvements are described by summarising the existing nesting method, improved nesting method, expected results, and metrics with which this improvement will be reviewed in Work Package 7. The content of each improvement is based on the designated roadmaps, designed in [MS6.1](#) (see [Annex](#)).

Note that not all MSCS listed in Section 2 of this report are part of this action.

As there is a wide variety of interface improvements, a list of keywords is compiled to categorise the interfacing improvements. These keywords are used in the title of each improvement.

<i>Keyword</i>	<i>Description</i>
BIAIS	Bias corrections
NEST	Nesting techniques
NUDG	Nudging
TECHN	Technical implementation
BETTER	Better numerics/physics
FORC	Surface forcing improvements
WAVE	Wave modelling, spectral info at boundary
ENS	Use of ocean ensembles

4.1 3D DCSM-FM

4.1.1 Thermobaricity effects in Equation of State [BETTER]

Thermobaricity effects in Equation of State	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	In deeper areas (>1 km) of the DCSM-FM domain, it has been observed that modelled vertical temperature and salinity profiles differ from those profiles observed in the GLORYS12V1 CMEMS ocean model and in situ observations. These differences occur because of inconsistencies in the resolved physics between the model software (DFlow-FM) and the GLORYS12V1 CMEMS model. In DFlow-FM, the EOS-80 equation of state was applied with the assumption of zero pressure. This implies that the stabilising effect of thermobaricity (pressure) is ignored, which causes more mixing throughout the water column, therefore deviating model outputs of salinity and temperature from observations.
Improved nesting	The pressure dependency has been added to the equation of state.

based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	These changes have been made computationally efficient and are publicly released in the software source code.
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The expected results are vertical temperature and salinity profiles closer to the GLORYS12V1 CMEMS ocean model and in situ observations, thereby making the ocean areas within the model domain more stable.
Metrics	RMSE (Vertical temperature and salinity profiles of GLORYS12V1 data and model data at locations near boundary)
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690055

Additional Information:

The functionality has been added to D-Flow FM, through incorporation of a new formulation of the Equation of State for the density. The existing EOS-80 formulation has been extended to EOS-83, which includes pressure dependence and thermobaric effects, and the addition has been made computationally efficient.

The EOS-80 formulation provides a standardised expression of seawater density, as a function of temperature and salinity at atmospheric pressure. This equation works with the assumption that the pressure is zero, interpreting the output as surface-referenced potential density. This assumptions are valid in shallow waters.

By updating the EOS-80 to EOS-83 formulation, the formulation becomes valid when pressure is non-zero (in deeper oceanic areas). This is consistent with modern oceanographic standards and ensures physically realistic behavior. For the full equation breakdown, see the D-Flow Flexible Mesh User manual, linked in the table above.

4.1.2 Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) forcing from gap-filled CMEMS [FORC]

Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) forcing from gap-filled CMEMS	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The current forcing file to initialise suspended particulate matter is a yearly average of MODIS satellite observations with a cosine function imposed on it to resemble seasonal variations (elevated SPM values in winter and lower SPM values in summer). This forcing resembles a 7-day averaged spatially static sediment field, where the values fluctuate, but the spatial distribution of the sediment plumes remains constant.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	A machine learning algorithm (4DVarNet—double LSTM) has been used to gap-fill satellite observations, resulting in spatially and temporally fluctuating SPM forcing fields based on weekly average CMEMS observations.
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The new forcing field is expected to be a more accurate and realistic SPM field, compared to the current forcing. As a result, it is expected to improve chlorophyll-a and primary production

	modelling in the MSCS.
Metrics	RMSE, R2 (Existing forcing and new forcing compared to CMEMS observations)
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15683195

Additional Information:

The gap-filling machine learning algorithm was trained on (a twice repeated) one year of daily modelled Total Inorganic Matter (TIM) data, retrieved from output of the 3D DCSM-FM, when sediment transport was actively modelled. This was considered the ground truth data. The patch data was created by masking the ground truth with clouds from the CMEMS dataset (OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L3_MY_009_113). This was done for two years of cloud data, resulting in two years of ground truth and patch data for training, which was then used to train and validate the model on (60% training, 40% validation). The model was tested on a weekly mean of the patch data.

To deal with the large domain and resolution of the 3D DCSM-FM, the 4DVarNet model was trained on the ground truth and patch data at a coarse resolution (~ 10 km x ~ 10 km). To apply the model to high resolution data (~1 km x ~1 km), the data was split into 25 different slices. The coarsely trained model was then applied to each of these slices, and they were merged together. This results in a gapfilled dataset of 1km resolution, with weekly SPM fields. The full workflow, with data details, is described in Figure 4.1.2.

Figure 4.1.2: Workflow overview of 4DVarNet Double LSTM gap-filling to create the observation-based SPM forcing.

4.2 Norkyst

4.2.1 Adjustment of hydrography on external boundary condition [BETTER]

Adjustment of hydrography on external boundary condition	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Currently we use daily means from the BAL-MFC and the ARC-MFC at the boundaries of Norkyst, adding tides and using the inverted barometer effect in post-processing and online during simulations to adjust the mean sea level.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>We use 4D-Var for data assimilation, and the lateral boundary conditions are part of the control vector. Hence we have an archive of analysis increments at the boundaries that reflect the inconsistencies between the CMEMS and the Norkyst physics. There is no obvious mean bias over time, but a slowly changing difference and often a mismatch in vertical structure. We will apply a correction scheme based on the latest analysis increments to be applied in the forecast cycle.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>We expect an improvement in the description of the hydrography, particularly in the open ocean areas.</p>
<p>Metrics</p>	<p>In situ salinity and temperature bias and RMSE.</p>
<p>Link to material</p>	<p>https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/coastal_system/boundary_conditions https://thredds.met.no/thredds/projects/foccus.html (see also D6.2 report) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700</p>

Additional Information:

Norkyst-DA is the assimilative version of the family of Norkyst models, producing forecasts daily for the Norwegian shelf seas. It uses ROMS-4DVAR (e.g. Iversen *et al.*, 2023) for data assimilation, ingesting satellite SST, insitu salinity/temperature, HF-radar radials during 48h analysis cycles. Forecasts from the ARC-MFC and BAL-MFC are used for lateral boundary conditions, with the latter only used for the portion of the boundary in the Kattegat. ROMS uses sigma type coordinates in contrast to the isopycnal coordinates of the ARC-MFC model HYCOM.

ROMS-4DVAR has the ability to adjust the lateral boundary conditions and the surface forcing as part of the assimilation procedure. An assessment of lateral boundary conditions analysis increments shows a slowly varying discrepancy between the internal Norkyst salinity and temperature fields and the imposed boundary conditions. A time varying bias correction will be applied to CMEMS boundary data used in the forecast cycle. This correction will be based on the latest analysis increments, using a prespecified timescale to limit memory in the procedure. An evaluation of the correction scheme will be done for a range of timescales from one day up to a month.

Figure 4.2.1 : Difference between external boundary condition values before and after the 4D-Var analysis, snapshot example on the model grid coordinates along the western boundary.

4.3 CROCO-MANGA

4.3.1 Open boundary perturbed ensemble [ENS]

Open boundary perturbed ensemble	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Following the current strategy of the HYCOM-based coastal system, the new CROCO-based coastal system is being set up with GLO-MFC products. Daily averaged 3D horizontal velocities and tracers are imposed with adaptive radiation conditions, and daily averaged barotropic velocities and sea surface height are imposed with Flather-type conditions. Inverse barometer effect from atmospheric pressure (ECMWF-ERA5) is used to correct free surface elevation.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Use of Global Ocean Physics Ensemble Reanalysis (GLO4ens; <i>provided by MOi but not distributed yet at CMEMS</i>) to produce regional ocean ensembles with consistent open boundary perturbations.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Capability to quantify the sensitivity of our regional system to uncertainties from remote regions.</p>

Metrics	Surface currents magnitude and direction with probabilistic approaches (e.g. ensemble mean and spread, continuous rank probability score (CRPS)).
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526387

Additional Information:

Our interfacing improvements aim at leveraging ensemble estimates of ocean state at global scale to force our coastal system at the boundaries. This is done with the Global Ocean Physics Ensemble Reanalysis (GLO4ens) currently developed at Mercator Ocean (MOi). It is a NEMO-based, ¼° ocean ensemble reanalysis providing 17-member ensemble-based probabilistic daily estimates of ocean state through model grid, sea-ice lateral melt and air temperature perturbations based on Brankart et al. (2015) and Leroux et al. (2022) methods.

From native NEMO model outputs provided by MOi, we converted this ensemble dataset into a CMEMS-like dataset in order to fit with the data format expected from our preprocessing tools used to derive open boundary conditions (i.e. https://croco-ocean.gitlabpages.inria.fr/croco_pytools/prepro/).

Our coastal system being currently interfaced with GLO12 products, a first consistency check consisted in comparing tracer transports across the boundaries (Fig. 1). It turns out GLO4ens systematically deviates from GLO12, the latter being only marginally included in the ensemble envelope of GLO4ens and showing a less pronounced variability over the considered period (Marsh 2019) . We are currently investigating solutions to leverage these ensemble estimates in a consistent way regarding these discrepancies.

This effort in producing boundary perturbed ensemble simulation complement the other ensemble approaches reported in Deliverable 6.2 “Processing Techniques”.

Figure 4.3.1: Integrated temperature (left) and salinity (right) transport across the three open boundaries of our regional system as derived from GLO12 (black) and GLO4ens (green).

4.4 Tolosa-SW

4.4.1 Filtering baroclinic dynamics [BETTER]

Filtering baroclinic dynamic	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The latest version of the French surge forecasting system is based on the shallow-water barotropic configuration of the Tolosa toolbox, computationally efficient to meet operational constraints. This implies that physical baroclinic processes such as waves and height/currents interactions (including wave setup) are not represented, and their impact on the simulated water levels is neglected.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The first approach consists of filtering the dynamics of IBI-ANFC and GLO-ANFC to extract baroclinic processes, such as dynamic variations in sea level or steric variations in sea level, excluding tides and atmospheric forcings.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Assessing the impact of unrepresented physical processes on simulated water levels will improve the representation of physics within the system, thereby increasing the accuracy of the forecasting system. Corrections are expected for the 2D fields, but</p>

	the incorrect representation of the wave setup will not be integrated.
Metrics	BIAS, MAE, RMSE, SD
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15537127

4.4.2 ML-assisted calibration method [BIAIS]

ML-assisted calibration method	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The latest version of the French surge forecasting system is based on the shallow-water barotropic configuration of the Tolosa toolbox, computationally efficient to meet operational constraints. This implies that the physical baroclinic processes such as waves and height/currents interactions (including wave setup) are not represented, and their impact on the simulated water levels is neglected.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The second approach is based on the development of a machine learning-assisted calibration method. Several algorithms are considered, such as Gradient Boosting or Long Short-Term Memory. These models use predictors related to 3D dynamics of CMEMS IBI-MFC outputs (such as sea surface temperature, eastwards / northwards velocity at the surface and sea surface height), together with sea state (Wave significant height and wave mean period) and tide gauges data (sea surface height).
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	Estimating the impact of unrepresented physical processes on simulated water levels through Machine Learning will reduce the bias on the predicted storm surge and improve the accuracy of the forecasting system. The corrective method will be applied on 1D time series only, and will take account of all 3D effects and wave/heights/currents interactions effects.
Metrics	BIAS, MAE, RMSE, SD
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15537127

Additional Information:

The French storm surge forecasting system, operated by Météo-France, uses the shallow water version of the Tolosa toolbox. It solves the non-linear shallow-water equations with source terms corresponding to bottom dissipation, tidal forcing, atmospheric pressure and surface wind. These equations are solved using the finite volume method, which enables the use of unstructured grids to achieve much finer resolutions. Consequently, the resolution varies spatially, ranging from 100 m in the English Channel and along the Atlantic coast to approximately 10-20 km in the northern part of the computational domain, off the Norwegian coast. The model uses low-dissipation

numerical schemes, which have been demonstrated to effectively calculate non-linear flows in the low-Mach (i.e. low-speed) regime (Couderc et al. 2017).

The open boundaries of the domain are forced with water levels from the FES2014b tidal model, and the tidal potential is also included in all simulations. The other domain boundaries are treated as vertical walls (zero flow), except for those corresponding to rivers for which flows are imposed, whether constant or not. Wind stress is represented in the model by a Charnock formulation with a constant drag coefficient. Finally, the effects of atmospheric pressure on water levels are represented by the inverse barometer.

4.5 GCOAST-GB

4.5.1 Extended nesting via spongelayer relaxation [NUDG]

Extended nesting via spongelayer relaxation	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The nesting approach is based on the downscaling from CMEMS products for the North West Shelf. The existing methodology uses NWS-MFC sea level, temperature, salinity and 3D currents at hourly frequency as lateral boundary conditions.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	In addition to the lateral boundary forcing larger domain nudging is deployed relaxing to T/S fields over a larger area. Also A similar approach for the nudging towards Sea surface SPM will be explored based on satellite Observations making a step towards data assimilation.
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The T/S nudging is expected to improve hydrodynamics and coast-to-open-sea dynamics while the SPM nudging should help increase accuracy of matter simulations.
Metrics	bias, rmse, correlation
Link to material	Existing nesting (updated for FOCCUS): https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15689870 Nudging: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15689988

Additional Information:

Classical boundary condition forcing is applied along the outermost row of grid elements for temperature, salinity, sea surface elevation, and horizontal currents. These boundary conditions typically involve time-varying data from a larger-scale model or observational dataset.

In extended simulations, internal model dynamics can lead to systematic drift, especially in tracer fields such as temperature and salinity. To counteract this, a relaxation (or nudging) scheme is implemented over a buffer zone extending approximately 20 km into the model domain from the open boundaries. This buffer typically corresponds to about 10 grid elements (indicated by the reddish area in Fig. 4.5.1).

Within this zone, the model solution is gently relaxed toward the external (parent) model values. The temporal evolution of any scalar tracer variable Φ (e.g., temperature or salinity) is modified according to the relaxation equation:

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \frac{\gamma}{\Delta t} (\Phi_{target} - \Phi)$$

where Φ is the simulated value within the nested model, Φ_{target} is the corresponding value from the outer (CMEMS NWS-MFC) model, Δt is the model time step, γ is a dimensionless relaxation coefficient, scaled such that the maximum nudging timescale is limited to 1 day (i.e., $\gamma=1$ corresponds to full relaxation within one day).

This formulation introduces a source term that reduces discrepancies with the parent model over time. By tapering the nudging strength inward from the boundary, it ensures numerical stability and maintains large-scale consistency while preserving interior small-scale dynamics.

Figure 4.5.1: Distribution of nudging strength factor γ .

4.6 GCOAST-BS

4.6.1 2D Wave Spectra forcing computed from CMEMS parameters [WAVE]

2D Wave Spectra forcing computed from CMEMS parameters	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Wave spectra are unavailable through CMEMS, and other data sources that provide wave spectra do not present enough resolution in the Black Sea (e.g., IFREMER WW3 hindcast). In this way, we need to run a basin-scale wave model only to produce spectral forcing at a few points to force our model. This required step before the target run demands time and computational resources, hampering the operability of GCOAST-BS.</p>

<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>We use wave parameters from CMEMS wave products to compute parametric 2D wave spectra for each time step at the model open boundary. The spectrum is calculated using the JONSWAP and Cartwright approach.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The parametric wave spectra will improve the GCOAST-BS workflow and allow a better interface with CMEMS. Additionally, this approach enables the use of the high-quality CMEMS Black Sea wave products, which assimilate data and are extensively validated. Despite its simplifications compared to the full wave spectrum, the parametric option has performed well when validated with observations in coastal areas.</p>
<p>Metrics</p>	<p>bias, RMSE, Pearson correlation</p>
<p>Link to material</p>	<p>The wave spectra is computed using <i>wavespectra</i> Python package, a Jupyter Notebook for demonstration is available at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690198</p>

Additional Information:

The 2D Wave Spectra is computed based on the CMEMS wave analysis and forecast parameters to generate spectral boundary conditions for the wave module of GCOAST-BS (WWM). The method gets the wave parameters available at CMEMS (wave significant wave height - SWH, wave mean direction - VMDB, and wave peak period - VTPK) on the open boundary points of the computational mesh. The directional wave spectra are then reconstructed at those points by applying the JONSWAP spectrum for frequency shape and the Cartwright method for directional spreading. The resulting 2D spectra (frequency and direction) at each boundary point and time step are stored and used as boundary conditions.

4.7 Lazio Coastal Areas

4.7.1 Increasing temporal frequency for open lateral boundary [TECHN]

Increasing temporal frequency for open lateral boundary	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The nesting approach is based on the downscaling from CMEMS products for the Mediterranean Sea. The existing methodology uses MED-MFC sea level at hourly frequency, and 3D daily current velocity, salinity and water temperature are used as lateral boundary conditions.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The new methodology for nesting the MSCS into the MED-PHY framework uses three-dimensional hourly data as lateral boundary conditions for all the variables. This includes current velocity, salinity, temperature, and sea level, thereby enhancing the temporal consistency and dynamical coherence of the nested simulations with respect to the large-scale circulation patterns</p>

	provided by the MED-PHY parent model.
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The use of higher-frequency lateral forcing—specifically, 3D hourly fields—will enhance the performance of the MSCS model. This improvement is particularly evident in the representation of surface temperature and current dynamics, as the increased temporal resolution allows the model to better capture sub-daily processes that are often smoothed out in lower-frequency forcing.
Metrics	BIAS, RMSE, Pearson correlation
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15638365

Additional Information:

We are developing and testing the use of hourly frequency lateral boundary forcing for both scalar and vector fields in the MSCS model. Currently, the MSCS is forced with daily fields for all variables, except sea level, which is already provided at an hourly resolution. The goal of this implementation is to enhance the dynamical representation of the system.

A preliminary 60-day simulation was carried out from 15 September to 14 November 2024. In the results presented below; the **Daily** configuration uses sea level at hourly frequency, while current velocity, salinity, and temperature are applied at daily resolution. The **Hourly** configuration applies hourly data for all lateral boundary variables, including 3D velocity, salinity, temperature, and sea level.

To quantify the impact of the forcing frequency, we assess the total kinetic energy (TKE), defined as

$$TKE = \int_{\Omega} \frac{U_i U_i}{2} d\Omega,$$

where Ω refers to the ocean volume in the nested domain, U_i is the i -th ocean current component and repeated indices imply summation over the U, V current components. The difference in TKE between two forcing scenarios is expressed as

$$\Delta TKE = \frac{TKE^h - TKE^d}{TKE^p},$$

where the superscripts h, d denote *hourly* and *daily* respectively. Note that this metric is normalized by the kinetic energy from the parent CMEMS products (superscript p).

Figure 4.7.1: (Top) Time series of Total Kinetic Energy (TKE) for **Daily** and **Hourly** cases. (Bottom) Time series of the difference between the two cases (ΔTKE).

Figure 4.7.1 presents the time series of the Total Kinetic Energy (TKE). While **Daily** results are capable of consistently predicting the occurrence and phase of major dynamic events (peaks of TKE), **Hourly** forcing naturally incorporates smaller-scale variability through the open boundaries, which bring their contribution to the transport dynamics within the nested domain. The impact of this finer-scale information is most evident in the amplitude of the TKE peaks, particularly during extreme events. For instance, in the present exercise, a non-negligible difference of $\Delta TKE \approx 75\%$ is recorded on day 2025-11-04.

4.8 DKSS

4.8.1 Nudging of T/S products [NUDG]

Nudging of T/S products	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	Current DKSS system has following weaknesses: i) the sea level lateral boundary condition only considers tide, surge and local static sea level; ii) lack of data assimilation which causes sub-surface T/S bias, especially in the Baltic Sea.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	We propose i) to use sea level prediction or reanalysis from CMEMS NWS MFC as boundary condition; ii) to nudge CMEMS Baltic-North Sea sub-surface T/S products from BALMFC and NWS MFC in DKSS
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	We expect that i) remote static impacts on sea level can be reflected in the NWS MFC products, so that sea level simulation in the HBM Baltic-North Sea will be improved; ii) BALMFC and NWS MFC assimilating T/S in the reanalysis, which should provide better products than non-assimilated HBM; by nudging the data, quality of sub-surface T/S in HBM will be improved.

Metrics	Error statistics such as bias, cRMSE and correlation of sea level and T/S will be used to quantify the improvements.
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696216

Additional Information:

A reference simulation using HBMs for a 3 year period 2014-2016 has been made without nudging CMEMS subsurface T/S . Figure below shows intercomparison of depth-dependent sea basin mean T/S bias in the Baltic Sea between HBMs and BALMFC reanalysis in which ICES T/S profiles was assimilated. The bias was calculated against available T/S profile observations include ICES data. HBMs0 has a cold bias up to -0.7C at 55m, a fresh bias up to 1.3psu at 65m. One can find that HBMs has a bias larger than CMEMS reanalysis. It is expected that after nudging CMEMS T/S, such bias in HBMs can be reduced.

Figure 4.8.1 Bias of HBMs horizontal mean water temperature and salinity in different depth in the Baltic Sea for reference simulation in 2014-2016, showing larger bias than CMEMS BAL MFC reanalysis in the subsurface.

4.9 OPTOS v3

4.9.1 Baroclinic Nested Downscaling and SST Bias Correction through Nudging. [NEST] [NUDG]

Baroclinic Nested Downscaling and SST Bias Correction through Nudging.	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The existing nested system of model domains currently lacks realistic baroclinic boundary forcing. The open-boundaries forcing for the NoS domain was based on climatological values for salinity and a zero horizontal gradient for temperature.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	1. Downscaling through Nesting:- The Improved COHERENS-based OPTOSv3.0 modeling system uses a nested hierarchy of one 2D and three 3D domains to simulate hydrodynamics in the Belgian coastal zone. The outermost CoSAM domain (2D) drives tidal and meteorological forcings into the nested 3D domains (NoS,

	<p>SoB, BeC). CMEMS NWS-FC products (Reanalysis and forecast) provide large-scale 3D boundary conditions for temperature and salinity to NoS.</p> <p>2. Bias Correction using a nudging technique: A nudging system for SST in NoS has also been implemented. These forcings are dynamically downscaled through progressively finer domains, ensuring consistency and detail from shelf to coast. BeC, the highest-resolution 3D domain (~145m), delivers localized forecasts with precise vertical and horizontal dynamics.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>A better resolved baroclinic circulation in the Belgian coastal zone with a reduced bias in SST.</p>
<p>Metrics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RMSE, bias and correlation coefficient r between model and observation by moorings. ● RMSE, bias and correlation coefficient r between model and satellite SST products. ● Optionally: Comparison between energy spectrum analysis as modeled and observed in moorings.
<p>Link to material</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706316</p>

4.10 SHYFEM-CNR

4.10.1 Spatially varying nudging of CMEMS T/S products [NUDG]

Spatially varying nudging of CMEMS T/S products	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The nesting approach is based on downscaling CMEMS products released at the regional scale of the Mediterranean Sea. MED-MFC sea level, current velocity, salinity, and water temperature are used as boundary conditions at the Otranto Strait.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Spatially varying nudging of T/S MED-REA over the whole Adriatic basin, where the value of the relaxation coefficient varies over the model domain.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The T/S nudging is expected to improve hydrodynamics and coast-to-open-sea dynamics.</p>
<p>Metrics</p>	<p>RMSE, bias and correlation coefficient between model and observation by in-situ monitoring stations.</p>
<p>Link to material</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1311736</p>

Additional Information:

MED-MFC physical assimilates, through a 3 variational data assimilation scheme (OceanVAR), temperature and salinity vertical profiles and satellite Sea Level Anomaly along track data. The nudging method is a flexible assimilation technique that is computationally more economical than other assimilation methods like variational data assimilation. In the nudging approach, a new source term is added to the prognostic equations that drag the results vs. the observed values. Therefore, it uses dynamical relaxation of the equations to tend to the observational points.

In our application, we are nudging (assimilating) MED-REA 3D fields of sea temperature and salinity during the simulation at all nodes of the unstructured grid of the Adriatic Sea. The value of the relaxation coefficient is spatially varying over the model domain (as a function of the grid resolution) from 2 days in the open sea and increasing, thus diminishing the restoration contribution, toward the coast. Therefore, the nudging allows the model state to be reconciled with the assimilated MED-REA data in the open sea, limiting error growth in the simulation, and to fully compute the hydrodynamics along the coast and in the coastal transitional environments (bays, deltas, estuaries and lagoons).

4.11 MOHID-LisOcean

4.11.1 Circulation and waves coupling up to coastal and estuary structure level [TECHN]

Circulation and waves coupling up to coastal and estuary structure level	
Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	Baroclinic 3D LisOcean model based on MOHID Water for the Lisbon Metropolitan Area with a horizontal resolution of 0.0028° downscaled from Global Copernicus model. Coupled with near-real time river discharges from Tagus and Sado rivers.
Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	The same existing nesting is already implemented including one-way coupling with SWAN, where UV velocities and sea surface height (SSH) are used to drive the wave model. Improvement includes coupling with wave models up to the coastal structure level (MOHID + SWAN + XBeach). Include watershed models around the estuarine area (MOHID Land). Test direct downscaling from IBI-MFC.
Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)	Operational implementation is expected to evolve towards a two-way coupling, where MOHID first forces SWAN, and then is re-run including wave-related outputs from SWAN to account for wave-current interactions.
Metrics	RMSE, bias and correlation coefficient between models and observations from tide gauges and other available in-situ monitoring stations.
Link to material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15756032

Additional Information:

In order to select the most suitable forcing dataset for the wave model, a comparison was carried out between simulations using the SWAN model forced with wave boundary conditions from both the IBI and the North Atlantic CMEMS products. The analysis showed that the differences in significant wave height results between the two products were minimal. Based on this, the IBI product was chosen to perform the coupling tests with the hydrodynamic model MOHID.

Three different configurations were evaluated:

- SWAN coupled with MOHID using both water level and currents,
- SWAN coupled using only water level from MOHID, and
- SWAN forced only by the IBI product, without coupling.

The results from each configuration were compared against observational data from the Lisbon Port buoy, located at Latitude: 38.6237° N, Longitude: -9.3880° W. The comparison is presented in the figure below.

Figure 4.11.1 Comparison between the significant wave height results from different implementations of SWAN model and Lisbon Port Buoy measurements.

In the above figure (4.11.1), the buoy measurements are shown in black, the uncoupled SWAN simulation (IBI only) in green, the fully coupled SWAN-MOHID simulation in blue, and the SWAN simulation coupled only with water level in red. Overall, the model appears capable of reasonably reproducing the observed wave signal, capturing the main variability patterns measured by the buoy.

The results show a slight improvement (0.01 for both RMSE and R^2) when both models (SWAN+MOHID) are coupled—i.e., when current and water level fields are included in the wave height simulations. In terms of bias, the fully coupled model also shows a reduction in systematic error, with a bias of -0.05 m compared to -0.10 m for the uncoupled version. This indicates that including hydrodynamic forcing reduces the average underestimation of wave heights, further supporting the benefit of model coupling. This improvement is observed despite the fact that the comparison was conducted over a relatively short time period.

4.12. AdriFS

4.12.1 Wave Spectra lateral boundary rebuild from CMEMS parameters [WAVE]

Wave Spectra lateral boundary rebuild from CMEMS parameters	
<p>Existing nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>Wave spectra are not directly provided by CMEMS products, primarily due to the substantial disk space required for their production and storage. As a result, a spectral approximation strategy is adopted for nesting the AdriFS model within the MED-WAV CMEMS product. In this approach, wave spectra are reconstructed from standard integrated wave parameters—such as significant wave height, peak period, and mean direction—by assuming a JONSWAP spectral shape and applying the directional spreading formulation proposed by Yamaguchi (1984). This method provides a reasonable approximation of the incoming wave energy. However, it does not account for spectral partitioning, meaning that the representation of complex sea states composed of multiple wave systems (e.g., wind sea and swell) remains limited.</p>
<p>Improved nesting based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The new method allows for the reconstruction of multiple spectral components. This enables a more realistic representation of complex sea states, including the coexistence of wind sea and swell systems. As a result, the input wave conditions used to drive the AdriFS model better reflect the true variability and structure of the wave field.</p>
<p>Expected Results based off MS6.1 (see Annex)</p>	<p>The use of multi-partitioned wave spectra is expected to improve the accuracy of wave simulations within the AdriFS forecasting system, particularly under conditions where the wave field exhibits multiple spectral peaks. This leads to more reliable forecasts, especially during complex sea state events, such as storms or rapidly changing wind conditions.</p>
<p>Metrics</p>	<p>BIAS, RMSE, Pearson correlation</p>
<p>Link to material</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15637958</p>

Additional Information:

The approach we present for downscaling the WW3 wave model in the MSCS focuses on a multi-partitioned method for reconstructing wave spectral boundary conditions. This method is evaluated against two alternative approaches: full spectral forcing and a standard single-peak reconstruction. The three methods are outlined below:

- Full Spectra Forcing (Reference Case):

This method provides the most accurate representation of wave conditions, as it retains the full spectral energy distribution. However, it requires a parent large-scale model to supply spectral boundary data, leading to high storage demands and limited practical availability.

- Rebuilding Spectra from Standard Mean Wave Parameters (Single-Peak Approach):

In this simplified downscaling method, the directional wave spectrum is reconstructed using only standard wave statistics — significant wave height (H_s), peak period (T_p), and mean wave direction (mDir).

A single spectral peak is assumed, using an approximation method that provides a reasonable estimate for the zeroth spectral moment. While computationally efficient and easy to implement, this approach does not capture the complexity of multi-modal sea states.

- Rebuilding Spectra from Partitioning (Multi-Partition Approach):

This method improves the spectral representation by reconstructing several distinct wave systems (e.g., wind-sea and 2–3 swell components).

Each partition is modelled using the Yamaguchi (1984) approximation and combined to form a complete, multi-peaked spectrum.

This reflects the physical nature of ocean waves as a superposition of monochromatic wave components traveling at different frequencies and directions, as described by the dispersion relation.

An example of the resulting spectra from each method is shown in figure 4.12.1, using polar plots. These plots highlight the differences in directional energy distribution between the reference and the single- and multi-partition approaches.

Figure 4.12.1 Comparison of the reference spectrum with spectra reconstructed using the multi-partition and single-peak methods for 2 random time steps (A and B).

This MSCS is also part of the evolution related to ensemble methods. Link for the software is in the table above, in the link to material.

4.13 Conclusion and Next Steps

To conclude, the numerous improvements described above have been implemented to better integrate CMEMS products into the various MSCS. Out of all improvements, four have implemented nudging techniques, three have improved the model numerics or physics, two use new wave modelling techniques and two have changed their technical implementation. The four other improvements use bias correction, update model surface forcings, use ensemble techniques or initialise nesting in CMEMS to improve the interfacing. Proof of implementation can be found in the corresponding sections and in D6.2. Also described here are the metrics, with which further steps will be taken.

The next steps are to test the new nesting techniques and validate the improvement to quantify the added value of the improved nesting techniques. This will be done using the metrics described in each improvement, over the duration of Work Package 7.

5. Annex

MSCS Inventory:

A preliminary inventory of coastal systems was agreed upon and created by the Consortium during the first year of the project, in order to better organize efforts to achieve the goals laid out in the DoA to improve them. A summary of this document can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, the Commission has the right to request access to this document directly using the project's shared drive here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1JxFKYBhboVHDFwAgmMikijJ_9N2UFUu6xNmFOAGB21M/edit?usp=sharing

This inventory includes a list of project partners, their relevant WPs and regions of interest, in addition to details about their coastal systems which are being used and developed in this project per the DoA. This includes the name of the systems, objectives for improvement, models used, current observations and forcing data, and how these systems interface with Copernicus Marine. Additionally, cross-WP connections for each coastal system are listed here, specifically how each has links to hydrology. Links to initial performance metrics for each coastal system are included here, in addition to roadmaps for improving each system's interfacing with Copernicus (detailed further below).

Milestone MS6.1: Interface Roadmaps for Improved Interfacing with CMEMS:

Roadmaps for improving each coastal system's interfacing with Copernicus was created in M6 of the project. A summary of this milestone can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, the Commission has the right to request access to the documents that make up this milestone directly using the project's shared drive here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1tlmc7NZxheF69ls86eIyiv3eLRsgggPH?usp=drive_link

These roadmaps include a summary of each member state coastal system, the Copernicus Marine model products used, as well as a description of the existing nesting method used. Crucially, these roadmaps detail for each coastal system the proposed improvements in this nesting, and will be used for the work outlined in the DoA in WP6/7.

6. References

- Agatova, A. I., Lapina, N. M., & Torgunova, N. I. (2008). Organic matter of the North Atlantic. *Oceanology*, 48(2), 182–195. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0001437008020045>
- Brankart, J. M., Candille, G., Garnier, F., Calone, C., Melet, A., Bouttier, P. A., ... & Verron, J. (2015). A generic approach to explicit simulation of uncertainty in the NEMO ocean model. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 8(5), 1285-1297. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1285-2015>
- Brzezinski, M. A. (1985). THE Si:C:N RATIO OF MARINE DIATOMS: INTERSPECIFIC VARIABILITY AND THE EFFECT OF SOME ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABLES. *Journal of Phycology*, 21(3), 347–357. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0022-3646.1985.00347.x>
- Couderc, F., Duran, A., Vila, J.-P. (2017). An explicit asymptotic preserving low Froude scheme for the multilayer shallow water model with density stratification. *Journal of Computational Physics* 343 (Supplement C) (2017) 235 – 270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2017.04.018>
- Iversen, S. C., Sperrevik, A. K., & Goux, O. (2023). Improving sea surface temperature in a regional ocean model through refined sea surface temperature assimilation. *Ocean Science*, 19(3), 729-744. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-19-729-2023>
- Leroux, S., Brankart, J. M., Albert, A., Brodeau, L., Molines, J. M., Jamet, Q., ... & Brasseur, P. (2022). Ensemble quantification of short-term predictability of the ocean dynamics at a kilometric-scale resolution: a Western Mediterranean test case. *Ocean Science*, 18(6), 1619-1644. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-18-1619-2022>
- Letscher, R. T., Moore, J. K., Teng, Y.-C., & Primeau, F. (2015). Variable C : N : P stoichiometry of dissolved organic matter cycling in the Community Earth System Model. *Biogeosciences*, 12(1), 209–221. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-12-209-2015>
- Moore, Andrew M., Hernan G. Arango, Gregoire Broquet, Brian S. Powell, Anthony T. Weaver, and Javier Zavala-Garay. (2011), "The Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS) 4-dimensional variational data assimilation systems: Part I—System overview and formulation." *Progress in Oceanography* 91(1), 34-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2011.05.004>
- Redfield, A. C. (1934). On the proportions of organic derivatives in sea water and their relation to the composition of plankton. In *James Johnston Memorial Volume* (pp. 176–192). University Press of Liverpool.